

Ceric Ion-amines as Redox Initiators in Vinyl Polymerisation

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The use of ceric salts in presence of various organic reducing agents, such as alcohols, thiols, glycols, aldehydes, and amines, as redox initiators in the polymerisation of monomers in aqueous solution has received much attention recently¹⁻². Some of the preliminary observations made with ceric ion-amine redox systems in the aqueous polymerisation of acrylonitrile and methyl methacrylate are recorded in the present communication.

Ceric ammonium sulphate in 2*N*-H₂SO₄ and triethylamine and ceric ammonium sulphate in 2*N*-H₂SO₄ and diethylamine were used as the redox systems. Monomers studied were acrylonitrile and methyl methacrylate in aqueous solution at 30°.

Procedure.—The reaction mixture was flushed with nitrogen to expel oxygen from the system before the addition of monomer. Even then, there was considerable inhibition period in all the experiments. The onset of polymerisation was indicated by the appearance of turbidity in the initially clear solution, the turbidity increasing with the progress of polymerisation till the complete precipitation of the polymer.

Ceric salt by itself was found to initiate polymerisation, but the presence of an amine considerably increased the rate of polymerisation, being directly proportional to the amine concentration. Triethylamine seemed to be more active than diethylamine; in a particular run, the yield of polymer obtained after 1 hour with triethylamine was almost twice that with diethylamine in the polymerisation of acrylonitrile under otherwise identical conditions. Graphical plotting of the experimental data shows the initial rate of polymerisation to be proportional to the first power of the monomer as well as of the amine concentration, but is independent of the initial concentration of ceric ion (Table I).

TABLE I

Dependence of R_p on Ce⁴⁺ ion concentration.

[Acrylonitrile] = 1.014 moles/litre. [Triethylamine] = 0.0166 mole/litre.

[H₂SO₄] = 0.166 mole/litre. Temp. = 30°.

[Ce ^{IV}] (moles/l)	0.03	0.01	0.005	0.0006
R _p × 10 ⁵ (moles l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)	2.680	2.640	2.640	2.695

This suggests that ceric ions are responsible for both initiation and termination of the polymer chains. The observations with ceric ion-amine systems are similar to those

1. Mino *et al.*, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1958 **31**, 242; 1959 **38**, 303; **39**, 523; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 1494
2. Katai *et al.*, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1963, Part C, No. 2, 463.

reported by Mino *et al.*¹ in the polymerisation of acrylamide,—initiated by ceric nitrate and 3-chlorol propan-1-ol redox systems.

Duke *et al.*³, postulated complex formation between ceric salts and alcohols or glycols; the disproportionation of the complex indicates the rate-determining step of the redox. This scheme was adopted by Mino *et al.*¹ and by Katai *et al.*² in their studies of ceric ion-alcohol and ceric ion-glycol systems, respectively. A similar complex formation between ceric salt and amines is tentatively suggested in our case and the following generalised reactions may be expected.

Capture of the free radicals by the monomer starts the chain reaction as follows:

where the symbols have their usual meanings.

The polymer formed from acrylonitrile with Ce^{4+} ion as initiator, with and without the amine, could not be dissolved in dimethylformamide, but it swelled to a gel-like structure. At the present stage of our work, it is difficult to ascribe this phenomenon either to cross-linking in the polymer or to its very high molecular weight. In the case of methyl methacrylate, however, the polymer obtained with this redox system could be dissolved with difficulty. Further work is in progress.

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Received August 2, 1965.